

PARTICIPANT HANDOUT (1.1.0)

RESILIENT TECHNOLOGIES

WHY DECADES-OLD TOOLS DEFINE THE ROOT OF MODERN RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT

Workshop Duration: 3 hours | Format: Hands-on with live demos

Lukas C. Bossert | IT Center, RWTH Aachen University

bossert@itc.rwth-aachen.de

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Geleitet durch:

Challenges

👉 Challenge 1: Your Second Literate Document (5 min)

1. Create a new file `my-meta-analysis.org` in your current working directory.
2. Add `#+TITLE:`, `#+AUTHOR:`, and `#+DATE:` metadata at the top.
3. Write a heading `* Data Overview` and a short sentence below it.
4. Insert an org-babel code block that runs `wc nfdi-analysis.org`.
5. Execute the block with `C-c C-c` and confirm the result appears as `#+RESULTS:`.

★ **Bonus:** What happens when you apply a name (`#+name: my-source`) to the org-babel source block? What is the benefit?

👉 Challenge 2: Explore the Zenodo API (5 min)

1. Query the full metadata record and pretty-print it:
`curl -sL "https://zenodo.org/api/records/15880071" | jq '.'`
2. Extract just the title and publication date:
`jq -r '.metadata.title, .metadata.publication_date'`

★ **Bonus:** Find out how many files are attached to this record: pipe through `jq '.files | length'`

👉 Challenge 3: Normalise a Second Pattern (5 min)

1. Check whether `NFDI4Ing` appears with alternate capitalisation using `grep -i`, then fix with `sed -i` if needed.
2. Use `sed -n` with the `p` flag to print *only* changed lines – without modifying the file.

★ **Bonus:** Chain two substitutions in one command using `-e`: `sed -e 's/A/B/' -e 's/C/D/'`

👉 Challenge 4: Validate and Count Your Own Consortium (5 min)

1. Pick any NFDI consortium (e.g. `NFDI4Chem`, `FAIRagro`, `Text+`).
2. Count how many lines mention it:
`grep -c 'YourConsortium' Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv`
3. List only lines where it appears *and* the collaboration is ongoing.
4. Save results to `results-YourConsortium/grep-summary.txt` (create the folder first with `mkdir -p`).

Hint:

```
grep -i 'NFDI4Chem' Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv | grep 'ongoing'
```

👉 Challenge 5: Audit Your Own Transformation (5 min)

1. Open the CSV in Emacs (`C-x C-f`), add a typo to line 5, save as `Collaboration_modified.csv` (`C-x C-w`).
2. Run `diff -u Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv Collaboration_modified.csv` and read the output.
3. Try `diff -q` (brief) and `diff -y` (side-by-side).
4. Save as a dated audit log: `diff -u ... > audit-$(date +%Y%m%d).patch`

Hint:

```
diff -u original.csv modified.csv > audit-$(date +%Y%m%d).patch
```

★ **Bonus:** Re-apply the patch: `patch original.csv audit-20250319.patch`. Test first with `patch --dry-run ...`

👉 Challenge 6: Extend the Makefile (≈5 min)

1. Activate the Markdown export by uncommenting the relevant `EXPORTS` line and run `make` – confirm `nfdi-analysis.md` is created.
2. Add a `test` target that runs only `execute` (no export).
3. Run `make -n` to do a dry-run and observe which commands *would* execute without running them.
4. What happens when you remove `-Q` from `EMACS_FLAGS`?

★ **Bonus:** Add a `help` target that prints each available target and a one-line description using `@echo`.

👉 Challenge 7: Aggregate Your Own Consortium (≈5 min)

1. Run `affiliation-count-by-type` for `NFDI4Chem` by changing only the `-v` value:

```
awk -f affiliation-count-by-type \
  -v consortium=NFDI4Chem \
  Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv
```

2. How many distinct collaboration types exist in the whole file? Use the hint one-liner and count the output lines.
3. Which consortium appears most often as Affiliated Lead/Chair (column 3)? Modify the one-liner to group by `$3` instead of `$1`, then pipe through `sort -t' ' -k2 -rn | head -5`.

Hint:

```
awk -F';' '{cnt[$1]++} END{for(t in cnt) print t, cnt[t]}' \
  Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv
```

★ **Bonus:** Filter by both consortium and status: add `:var status="ongoing"` to the header and change the pattern to `$0 ~ consortium && $0 ~ status`.

👉 Challenge 8: Archive and Verify Your Results (≈5 min)

1. Create a `.tar.gz` archive:


```
tar -czf my-results.tar.gz results-YourConsortium/
```
2. Generate a SHA-256 checksum:


```
sha256sum my-results.tar.gz | tee my-results.tar.gz.sha256
```
3. List the archive contents:


```
tar --list -f my-results.tar.gz
```
4. Extract into a new folder to verify:


```
mkdir verify/ && tar -xzf my-results.tar.gz -C verify/
```
5. Compare the checksum of the re-extracted CSV with the original.

★ **Bonus:** Use `tar --exclude='*.bak'` to create a clean archive omitting backup files – useful when preparing a dataset for public deposit.

★ **Bonus:** Use `diff` from earlier to compare the files.

Quick Reference --- All Demo Commands

org-babel code block

```
#+name: the folder structure of HOME
#+begin_src bash :eval yes :results verbatim
ls ~ | head -2
#+end_src
```

org-mode for spreadsheets

```
#+name: Overview of consortia and research areas
| domain | consortia | datasets | avg | % |
|-----+-----+-----+-----+-----|
| Life Sciences | 8 | 123 | 15 | 13.6 |
| Humanities | 6 | 150 | 25 | 16.6 |
| Engineering Sc. | 5 | 173 | 35 | 19.1 |
| Natural Sciences | 7 | 458 | 65 | 50.7 |
|-----+-----+-----+-----+-----|
| TOTAL | 26 | 904 | | |
#+TBLFM: @>$2=vsum(@2$2..@-1$2);%.0f::@>$3=vsum(@2$3..@-1$3);%.0f
#+TBLFM: @2$4..@-1$4=$3/$2;%.0f::@2$5..@-1$5=100*$3/@>$3;%.1f
```

download with progress and resume

```
#+name: retrieve-source-file
#+begin_src bash
curl -L -O -#
↪ "https://zenodo.org/records/15880071/files/Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv" &&
↪ echo "file downloaded."
#+end_src
```

query Zenodo API

```
#+name: curl-checksum
#+begin_src bash
curl -sL "https://zenodo.org/api/records/15880071" |
jq -r '.files[] | select(.key="Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv") | .checksum' |
↪ awk -F: '{print $2}'
#+end_src
```

checksum of local file

```
#+name: file-checksum
#+begin_src shell
md5sum Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv | awk '{print $1}'
#+end_src
```

checksum comparison

```
#+name: compare-checksums
#+begin_src bash :var remote=curl-checksum :var local=file-checksum
[[ "$remote" = "$local" ]] && echo -n "MATCH: $local" || echo "MISMATCH"
#+end_src
```

clean data with backup

```
#+name: sed-cleaning-delimiter
#+begin_src bash
sed -i.bak 's|NFDI-NFDI-MatWerk|NFDI-MatWerk|g' \
Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv \
&& echo "file cleaned."
#+end_src
```

verify cleaning

```

#+begin_src bash :results verbatim
grep -ci 'NFDI-NFDI-MatWerk' Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv \
  || echo "file properly cleaned."
#+end_src

```

complex pattern matching

```

#+begin_src bash :results verbatim
grep -E "^Event:(.+?)MatWerk(.+?);ongoing$" Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv | head
↵ -1
#+end_src

```

compare files

```

#+name: diff-csv
#+begin_src bash :results output
diff -u -U0 Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv.bak
↵ Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv | head -5
#+end_src

```

makefile for the project

```

PROJECT = nfdi-analysis
EMACS   ?= emacs
ORGFIL  := $(PROJECT).org
SHELL   := bash

# -- Export formats -----
EXPORTS += -f org-ascii-export-to-ascii # → .txt
EXPORTS += -f org-md-export-to-markdown # → .md
EXPORTS += -f org-html-export-to-html   # → .html

# -- Shared Emacs flags -----
EMACS_FLAGS = -Q --batch
EMACS_FLAGS += -l org -l ob -l ob-shell -l ob-awk -l ob-org
EMACS_FLAGS += "$(ORGFIL)"
EMACS_FLAGS += --eval "(setq org-confirm-babel-evaluate nil)"

.PHONY: all execute export clean

all: execute export
@echo "* done *"

execute:
@echo "* evaluating source blocks in $(ORGFIL) *"
$(EMACS) $(EMACS_FLAGS) \
  --eval "(org-babel-execute-buffer)" \
  --eval "(save-buffer)"
@echo "* source blocks evaluated *"

export:
@echo "* exporting $(ORGFIL) *"
$(EMACS) $(EMACS_FLAGS) \
  --eval "(setq org-export-use-babel nil)" \
  --eval "(setq org-html-htmlize-output-type nil)" \
  $(EXPORTS)
@echo "* exported *"

clean:
@rm -f $(PROJECT).txt $(PROJECT).md $(PROJECT).html
@echo "* cleaned *"

```

count collaboration types (bash block)

```

#+name: awk-with-bash
#+begin_src bash :results verbatim
awk -F';' '/NFDI-MatWerk/ {cnt[$1]++; total++}
  END{
    print "---- NFDI-MatWerk ----"
    for(t in cnt) print t, cnt[t]
    print "TOTAL:", total}' Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv
#+end_src

```

awk source block

```

#+name: affiliation-count-by-type
#+begin_src awk :in-file Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv :var
↳ consortium="NFDI-MatWerk" :results verbatim
BEGIN { FS = ";" }
$0 ~ consortium { cnt[$1]++; total++ }
END {
  print "---- " consortium " ----"
  for (t in cnt) print t, cnt[t]
  print "TOTAL:", total
}
#+end_src

```

reuse for a different consortium

```

#+call: affiliation-count-by-type(consortium="NFDI4ING")

```

write result to file

```

#+name: affiliation-count-to-file
#+begin_src awk :in-file ../Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv :var
↳ consortium="NFDI4Chem" :results file :dir results-NFDI4Chem :mkdirp yes :file
↳ analysis-overview.txt
BEGIN { FS = ";" }
$0 ~ consortium { cnt[$1]++; total++ }
END {
  print "---- " consortium " ----"
  for (t in cnt) print t, cnt[t]
  print "TOTAL:", total
}
#+end_src

```

reuse write-to-file for a different consortium

```

#+call: affiliation-count-to-file[:dir results-NFDI4ING](consortium="NFDI4ING")

```

create archive with checksum

```

#+name: archive-files
#+begin_src bash :results verbatim
tar -czf NFDI-results.tar.gz \
  makefile *.org \
  Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv \
  Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv.bak \
  results-*/ \
  && echo "file tape-archived."
sha256sum NFDI-results.tar.gz | tee NFDI-results.tar.gz.sha256
#+end_src

```

list archive

```

#+name: list-archive-files
#+begin_src bash
tar --list -f NFDI-results.tar.gz | sort
#+end_src

```